

THE REDUCTION OF AMMONIUM MOLYBDATE BY L-SODIUM HYDROGEN ASCORBATE IN THE DARK.

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The reduction of ammonium molybdate by *l*-sodium hydrogen ascorbate has been studied in the dark. It has been found that when the concentration of sodium hydrogen ascorbate and ammonium molybdate are equivalent, the velocity of reaction is a maximum. For excess concentrations of either reagent, the velocity is less. This indicates that the velocity of reaction is proportional to the concentration of the complex formed by the association of an equivalent of ascorbate with one equivalent of molybdate.

Ascorbic acid, since its isolation in the pure state, has been a material of absorbing interest. During the past few years a large amount of work has been done on the physiological action as well as on the various physicochemical properties of ascorbic acid. Herbert and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1270) made for the first time a careful investigation of some of the physicochemical properties of ascorbic acid obtained from nature. Ghosh and Rakshit (*Biochem. Z.*, 1936, 289, 15; 1937, 289, 395; 1938, 297, 153) and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1B, 1) made a detailed investigation of the physicochemical properties of synthetic *l*-ascorbic acid and dehydro-ascorbic acid. The present investigation was carried out to study in details, reduction of ammonium molybdate with sodium hydrogen ascorbate.

It was found that just on mixing the ascorbate with ammonium molybdate a yellow colour is developed which with time becomes green due to reduction of the molybdate. The yellow colour of the mixture is due to the formation of a complex.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The reaction cell ($4 \times 4 \times 0.5$ cm.) made of plane glass plates fused into one another with a stopper at the top was placed inside a double jacketed metal box. The temperature was kept constant by passing, with the aid of a circulating pump, water from a thermostat through the annular space of the box.

Reagents.—*L*-Light's extra pure synthetic *l*-ascorbic acid; Merck's extra pure ammonium molybdate and NaOH and resublimed iodine were used. For making solutions redistilled water was used.

Since ascorbic acid or an ascorbate is easily oxidised by air in presence of moisture, fresh solutions of ascorbic acid was prepared every time just before each experiment. Sodium hydrogen ascorbate was prepared every time by adding an equivalent of NaOH to ascorbic acid solution. It is known that p_H value of sodium hydrogen ascorbate is near about 6. The p_H value of ammonium molybdate was determined electrometrically using a quinhydrone electrode and adjusted to 6. On mixing sodium hydrogen ascorbate to ammonium molybdate the p_H will remain nearly constant.

Since it is very difficult to determine accurately the p_H of ascorbic acid or an ascorbate the principle of isohydry was adopted in keeping the p_H constant.

Determination of the Velocity of Reaction.—The velocity of reaction was determined by pipetting out 0.36 c.c. of the reaction mixture in a conical flask containing 5 c.c. of *N*-HCl and then estimating the ascorbic acid with 0.0122 *N*-iodine solution by means of a microburette. It is to be noted here that iodine cannot oxidise the reduced molybdate formed. The experimental data are recorded in Table I. The reaction has been studied only up to 10-15% conversion. In Table I, $\Delta x/\Delta t \cdot 10^4$ has been tabulated where $\Delta x/\Delta t$ represents the change in concentration of

0.36 c.c. of ascorbic acid per minute in terms of c.c. of 0.0112*N*-iodine. [Mo]=concentration of ammonium molybdate in g. equivalents per litre, the equivalent weight of molybdate being calculated on the basis of one equivalent containing one g. atom of molybdenum.

TABLE I.

Effect of varying the concentrations of both ammonium molybdate and sodium hydrogen ascorbate.

$\mu_n = 6.0$ Temp. = 29°.				
Conc. of sodium hydrogen ascorbate in normality.				
	0.025	0.05	0.05	0.1
	Conc. of Mo = 0.05 <i>N</i> .			
$\Delta x / \Delta t \times 10^4$	5.5	9.8	7.7	4.3
Colour	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Yellow (original colour) of the completed
	Conc. of Mo = 0.05 <i>N</i> .			
$\Delta x / \Delta t \times 10^4$	3.3	14.4	39.0	20.9
Colour	Green	Green	Green	Greenish yellow
	Conc. of Mo = 0.1 <i>N</i> .			
$\Delta x / \Delta t \times 10^4$	2.81	14.2	40.0	145.0
Colour	Green	Green	Green	Green

DISCUSSION.

It is remarkable that when the concentrations of sodium hydrogen ascorbate and ammonium molybdate are equivalent the velocity of reaction is maximum. This indicates that the velocity of reaction is proportional to the concentration of the complex formed by the association of one equivalent of ascorbate with one of molybdate. For excess concentrations of either reagent the velocity diminishes which goes to show that the complex is stabilised by both molybdate and ascorbate. This conclusion is further supported by the fact that for equivalent concentrations

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k [\text{complex}] = k' (A - x) (B - x)$$

where *A* and *B* represent conc. of molybdate and ascorbate and *x* = complex formed.

If *x* is small compared with *A* or *B*, and when *A* = *B*,

$$\left[\frac{dx}{dt} \right]_1 = k' \cdot A^2, \quad \left[\frac{dx}{dt} \right]_2 = k' \cdot A^2,$$

From Table I we see that for 0.025*N* concentrations of both ascorbate and molybdate,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = 9.8 \times 10^{-4}$$

and for 0.05*N* concentrations of both molybdate and ascorbate $dx/dt = 39.0 \times 10^{-4}$ and for 0.1*N* concentrations of both molybdate and ascorbate, $dx/dt = 145.0 \times 10^{-4}$. These results support the mechanism suggested.

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